

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>SEE Test of the Magnetometer Front-End ASIC</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA09-278</i>
General application	<i>Space, Physics Instrumentation, Magnetometry</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Werner Magnes, Space Research Institute of the Austrian Academy of Sciences</i>
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Date(s) of the experiment	<i>07.03.2024</i>
Facility	<i>Heavy Ions Facility at the Cyclotron Resource Center of the Université Catholique de Louvain</i>
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	<i>8h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The Magnetometer Front-End ASIC 4 (MFA-4), developed by the Space Research Institute (IWF) of the Austrian Academy of Sciences in cooperation with the Institute of Electrical Measurement and Sensor Systems (EMS) of Graz University of Technology, integrates most of the analog front-end electronics needed for operating a fluxgate magnetometer into a single microchip. It improves upon its predecessor by providing the Digital-to-Analog Converter (DAC), which is the most critical component of a fluxgate magnetometer's signal path, with a signal-to-noise-ratio of 111dB and a total harmonic distortion of -95dB also in Earth's magnetic field, while enhancing Single Event Effects (SEE) tolerance. As this chip is intended to fly on space missions, its response to environmental conditions such as radiation exposure is crucial. Therefore, it was tested against radiation influences, in particular to find out its performance and artifacts occurring due to SEEs.

The main objectives of the test have been to determine the Linear Energy Transfer threshold (LET_{TH}) and saturation cross-section (σ_{SAT}) of the analog and digital part of the ASIC. All of the circuits reside on a silicon die which is packaged in a ceramic carrier. A printed circuit board (PCB) carrying the chip, power supply and communication electronics as well as all instrumentation and protection circuits is mounted in the beamline, exposing the die (3040 μm x 1520 μm) to a heavy ion beam with at least 5 mm diameter with sufficient uniformity (+/-10% in fluence and particle energy). In order to provide a LET range relevant for space electronics, values in the range of 5 to 60 MeV cm^2/mg (in silicon) and a particle flux in the range of 100 to 10000 ions/ cm^2/s are required.

Experiment test report

The test setup used to achieve the objectives consists of a Radiation Board mounted directly in the vacuum chamber of the beamline, connected through a vacuum feedthrough to a Power Supply Unit (PSU) and an Adapter Board outside the chamber. The Adapter Board holds a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) which handles digital control and communication to the Radiation Board and the Heavy Ion Facility (HIF) beam as well as interfaces to a Raspberry Pi single board computer, used to store the measurement data for postprocessing and to provide a network interface for live data visualization as well as test setup control. A PC was used to control and monitor the setup during irradiation of the chip.

Besides communication interfaces to the chip and monitoring units for all operational currents and voltages, the Radiation Board provides six distinct latch-up protected power supply channels providing 1.8 V and 3.3 V to respective supply lines of the digital and analog part of the test chip. Both analog and digital over-current triggers can be selected to initiate a latch-up handling routine which includes controlling the shutter of the HIF, power down and reboot of the chip as well as digital control of its operational mode. Occurrences of latch-ups are counted for each power supply channel. Figure 1 depicts an overview of the setup.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Test Setup

In order to modify the LET introduced by the ions, the HIF is able to tilt the Radiation Board up to an angle of 45 degrees. In preparation for the test, the software SRIM [1] was used to determine the LET achievable by the available ion species and tilts at the HIF, considering the actual composition of the metallization and isolation layers on top of the doped silicon in the die. The overview given in Figure 2 served as a guide for selecting beam parameters and tilts during the tests. Examinations of a previous iteration of the chip in a proton beam facility concluded that no latch-up occurred below an LET of around 12 MeV cm²/mg, defining a start LET for the sweep with heavy ions. To test this assumption for the current iteration of the chip, an irradiation run with aluminium ions was conducted, as their range

lies just below 12 MeV cm²/mg.

Figure 2: Achievable LET vs. Ion Species

Tests were conducted with four Devices Under Test (DUT) with serial numbers MFA4v4Q002, MFA4v4Q007, MFA4v4Q009, MFA4v4Q010. The dies packaged in these DUTs were produced on a 180 nm mixed signal process, incorporating low-noise CMOS structures which reside upon dedicated doped wells.

In the first run with MFA4v4Q002, ions of Al, Ar, Cr, Kr and Xe were tested at both 0 and 45 degrees of tilt to scan for the Linear Energy Transfer threshold for Single Event latch-ups (LET_{TH, SEL}). The mean flux, set at its maximum value, ranged from 9329 ions/cm²/s (Cr ion at 45 degrees) to 15633 ions/cm²/s. Irradiations on MFA4v4Q002 and MFA4v4Q007 were conducted up to a fluence of around 1E6 ions/cm². During the first irradiation runs, the analog latch-up over-current protection was triggered while no over-current was recorded by the current monitoring unit. This yielded the conclusion that the analog over-current trigger was too noise sensitive for the HIF environment. Further tests were conducted with the digital over-current triggers, which utilize filtered signals from data acquired through the current monitoring unit.

As there was no real occurrence of a latch-up, the next DUT, MFA4v4Q007 was tested directly with Xe ions at a tilt of 45 degrees to provide the highest LET possible. Again, no latch-up during irradiation was detected.

These first results suggest that the chip is immune to latch-ups up to a LET of around 100 MeV cm²/mg. While this finding does not exactly fulfil the goal of finding LET_{TH, SEL}, it still answers the underlying question of how well the chip withstands radiation-induced latch-ups.

Nevertheless, while no latch-up could be triggered, there were still occurrences of Single-Event Upsets (SEU) and Single-Event Transients (SET) evident in the live view and logged time series of current and voltage monitoring data. A special focus lies on the output current of the DAC, which includes close to all of the digital and analog signal path present on the chip and serves as a good indication of SEEs. For further characterization of these SEEs, the DUT MFA4v4Q009 was irradiated with ions starting at Xe at 45 degrees tilt, progressing downwards in ions, tilt and LET until no SEU or SET occurred. This LET sweep stopped at Ar, 35 degrees of tilt (~13 MeV cm²/mg).

The next DUT, MFA4v4Q010 was irradiated with a LET sweep starting at Ar, 35 degrees tilt (~13 MeV cm²/mg), up to Xe, 45 degrees tilt (~100 MeV cm²/mg). Both LET sweeps of MFA4v4Q009 and MFA4v4Q010 were conducted up to a fluence of 5E6 ions/cm² in order to obtain cleaner statistics of occurring SEEs.

For the time series of the output current, three main types of SEE were identified, namely spikes (Figure 3), steps (Figure 3) and functional interrupts (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Spike and Step

The spike seen in Figure 3 can be explained either by bit flips in continuously overwritten digital blocks in the DAC or by transients in the analog part of the signal path. However, the exact cause can not be investigated, as it would involve reading back digital registers to confirm or rule out bit flips. However, the MFA-4's digital interface is only designed to be written.

In order to achieve higher precision by oversampling, a Cascaded-Integrator-Comb (CIC) filter is connected between the external digital interface and the digital input of the DAC. Such a filter contains multiple integrators, which open the possibility of accumulating a bit flip in the digital value. Such an accumulation manifests as a permanent step in the output of the DAC, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Functional Interrupt

Another reoccurring effect observed was the DAC ceasing operation altogether, with the current output taking arbitrary values with step-like transitions until finally reaching zero after around ten seconds. While this effect definitely is caused by a bit flip in the digital part of the DAC, it is classified as a Single Event Functional Interrupt (SEFI), since it could only be resolved by resetting the whole chip. All observed SEEs can be classified into ~82% spikes, ~13% steps, ~4% SEFIs and less than 1% unclassified signatures. From the numbers of SEEs counted, each SEE class can be assigned a cross-section, which serves as a measure for how many SEEs occur per particle fluence. Table 1 outlines the counts and calculated cross-sections of for all irradiation runs.

Table 1: SEE Statistics and Cross-Sections

Run	DUT	ION	Tilt [deg.]	AR LET metallized [MeV cm ² /mg.]	AR LET unmetallized [MeV cm ² /mg.]	output current (dig value)	#pos spikes	# neg spikes	# spike to 0 no step	# spike to 0 with step	#pos steps	#neg steps	#output dead	#long spike/output dead	#un-classified	#Spikes	#Steps	#SEUs	#SEEs	fluence [f/cm ²]	Spike cross-section [cm ²]	Output Dead cross-section [cm ²]	Steps cross-section [cm ²]	
0	Q002	Al	0	6.5984	6.2025	max+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1			
1	Q002	Al	45	9.3744	8.9834	max+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		
2	Q002	Ar	0	11.8272	11.4500	max+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		
3	Q002	Ar	45	17.4406	16.5613	max+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1		
4	Q002	Cr	0	18.2291	17.5726	max+	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	Q002	Cr	45	26.9812	25.5574	max+	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	Q002	Kr	0	36.5394	35.4409	max+	3	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	Q002	Kr	45	53.4945	51.2372	max+	7	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	Q002	Xe	0	70.0987	68.7416	max+	2	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	Q002	Xe	45	100.5362	98.7478	max+	15	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	Q007	Xe	45	100.5362	98.7478	max+/max-	12	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	Q009	Xe	45	100.5362	98.7478	max+	14	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	Q009	Xe	0	70.0987	68.7416	max+	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	Q009	Kr	0	36.5394	35.4409	max+	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	Q009	Kr	45	53.4945	51.2372	max+	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	Q009	Kr	45	26.9812	25.5574	max+	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	Q009	Cr	0	18.2291	17.5726	max+	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	Q009	Ar	0	11.8272	11.4500	max+	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	Q009	Ar	45	17.4406	16.5613	max+	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	Q009	Ar	35	14.7404	14.1679	max+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
20	Q009	Ar	40	15.9274	15.2187	max+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21	Q010	Ar	40	15.9274	15.2187	max+	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	Q010	Ar	35	14.7404	14.1679	max+	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
23	Q010	Ar	25	13.1955	12.7337	max+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	Q010	Ar	45	17.4406	16.5613	max+	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25	Q010	Cr	45	26.9812	25.5574	max+	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
26	Q010	Cr	0	18.2291	17.5726	max+	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
27	Q010	Kr	0	36.5394	35.4409	max+	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
28	Q010	Kr	45	53.4945	51.2372	max+	7	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
29	Q010	Xe	0	70.0987	68.7416	max+	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
30	Q010	Xe	45	100.5362	98.7478	max+	11	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

When the cross-section for spikes σ_{Spike} is empirically fitted to a Weibull curve of the form $\sigma = \sigma_{\text{SAT}} (1 - e^{-(\text{LET} - \text{LET}_{\text{TH}})/w})^s$, a threshold $\text{LET}_{\text{TH, Spike}} = 13 \text{ MeV cm}^2/\text{mg}$ and a saturation cross-section $\sigma_{\text{SAT, Spike}} = 2.786\text{E-}6 \text{ cm}^2$ arise together with the fit parameters $w = 55$ and $s = 0.6$, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Spike cross-section

In conclusion, a good characterisation of the response of the chip to a broad range of LETs was possible. With the result of the chip being immune to latch-ups up to around 100 MeV cm²/mg, the technology’s readiness to be used in space was shown. Various “soft” SEEs, which do not pose a threat to the operability of the chip have been observed and could be mitigated in higher level instrument design or by including on-chip redundancy.

Further investigation would include test structures to further narrow down error sources as well as experiments involving an amount of total ionizing dose (TID) to broaden the knowledge about the radiation response of the chip.

[1] www.srim.org

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an ‘X’ next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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